

ISic3287

I.Sicily inscription 3287

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 281

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ΣΕΙΝ ΜΜ,Ζ παρακι
2. μένην τῷ ναῷ Ἰλαρ[ί]ω
3. νος

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (eng)

...set up before the naos, Hilarios

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645555

PHI 316271

Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle

collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 189

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3287. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358055>